

IMPROVING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE AS A COMPONENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE: LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. *This article provides an analysis of scientific-methodical literature on the problem of improving grammatical competence. The author defines concepts such as competence and grammatical competence, and also briefly discusses the role of grammar in learning a foreign language.*

Keywords: *grammar, method, approach, English language, skill, competence, innovative technology.*

Today, the problem of teaching foreign languages, in particular English, is relevant due to the expanding scale of influence of the globalization process on all spheres of society. The process of teaching English as a foreign language includes, in addition to other aspects, the development of grammatical competence, which forms the basis of communicative competence. Grammar, at its core, is the cohesive component of language, without which a sentence becomes a mere collection of words. Based on this, English teachers are faced with two main problems: which aspect of the language to prioritize and which method to choose to improve it. Modern linguistics no longer requires the creation of completely new methods and technologies for teaching a foreign language; philological researchers are tasked with comparing, contrasting and finding ways to integrate various methods, thereby opening the way to innovation. To resolve this issue, it is necessary to turn to the scientific and methodological literature and analyze the existing material.

According to B.V. Belyaev, "it is no necessary so much to know the rules about how you can and should construct foreign language sentences, as to practically master various grammatical constructions (models and structures) in your speech. The decisive factor in such assimilation is foreign language speech practice". [1, p. 141] Ghez and others, in a book on methods of teaching foreign languages, also argue that "with a limited number of hours allocated to learning a foreign language, practically significant results can be obtained only if the teacher pays primary attention to the implementation of the communicative task" [2, p. 39]. A similar opinion is also expressed by researcher I.F. Musaelyan, who notes that "it is impossible to establish the priority of grammar over vocabulary or vice versa. Without knowledge of the grammatical structure of a language, it is impossible to solve communicative problems in a foreign language. However, assimilation of the grammatical system of a language occurs, as a rule, only on the basis of familiar vocabulary" [3, p. 139-142]. The above works highlight the importance of developing communicative practice as a key condition for successful mastery of a foreign language, both in psychological and methodological aspects.

Giving a significant place to the process of communication and highlighting it as the main means of developing language and speech skills, the communicative approach is a universal method in which different channels are used to receive (vision, hearing) and exchange

(conversation, facial expressions) information in foreign language classes. Within the framework of this approach, the grammar of a foreign language is not taught in the form of memorizing rules and forms, but is studied in the process of speech practice, when knowledge of grammatical phenomena is demonstrated in communicative situations. At the same time, according to L.I. Karpova, for the successful use of grammatical skills not only in educational speech, but also in natural situations, it is necessary to take into account social, semantic and discursive factors. Their interaction with grammar involves the development of grammatical competence in close connection with other aspects of the language. [4, p. 43-45] Consequently, the communicative approach, emphasizing the practice of communication and thus developing speech skills, simultaneously forms grammatical skills, as a result of which communicative grammatical competence develops.

Frolova and Shchukin, discussing the methodology for developing grammatical competence, in addition to inductive and deductive approaches, also highlight the lexical method of mastering grammatical material, which, in their opinion, is relevant for the initial stage of teaching a foreign language, “when the stock of grammatical knowledge is not yet large and the grammatical unit is actually learned as a lexical unit” [5, p. 150]. The authors also highlight the mistake that most teachers make in focusing solely on grammar rather than language skills. As a result, due to insufficient communicative practice, students experience uncertainty when speaking in a foreign language, which leads to various speech errors. [5, p. 156] Of course, grammar plays an important role in learning a foreign language, but the ultimate goal in this process should be the formation of communicative competence, which is achieved by improving grammatical skills. This view is also expressed by researcher Danko, who argues that “communicative competence constitutes the “core” of foreign language learning in the form of knowledge, skills and abilities developed and includes private competencies, one of which is grammatical.” [6, p. 98-103]. His point of view is supported by another researcher L.E. Ostapova, noting that “grammatical skills are an important element in the development of students’ communicative competence, since it is impossible to consider mastering the grammatical side of foreign language speech in isolation from the communication process” [7, p. 429-432].

In the book on methods of teaching foreign languages, L.R. Sakaeva and A.R. Baranova argue that studying the grammar of a foreign language “helps to better understand the grammatical structure of the native language, develops logical thinking, observation, the ability to analyze and generalize, i.e. in the process of studying it, developmental, educational goals of training are realized.” They also divide grammatical skills into two types: productive and receptive. Productive grammatical skill is understood as “the speaker’s ability to choose a model adequate to the speech task,” receptive grammatical skill is expressed as “the ability of the reader (listener) to recognize the grammatical forms of the language being studied and relate them to their meaning.” Accordingly, the first manifests itself in the process of speaking or writing, while the latter is associated with reading and listening skills. This division of grammatical skill is the basis for their identification of two main goals when teaching the grammar of a foreign language, according to I.L. Bim: “firstly, to teach students to formulate their oral statements grammatically correctly, while concentrating on the content; secondly, to teach students to recognize grammatical phenomena when reading and listening.” [8, p. 66-68] Mastery of both grammatical and lexical knowledge in foreign language communication is important for the development of not only productive, but also receptive skills, since, as noted by I.F. Musaelyan, “one can competently

construct his or her own statement using a fairly limited set of words and grammatical structures, but this does not guarantee that other people will not use more complex structures in their speech, which can become a serious obstacle to understanding the essence of the statement” [3, p. 139-142]. Researchers thus highlight the relevance of the problem of developing the lexicogrammatical component of language competence, the insufficient level of development of which can lead to serious gaps of a communicative and sociolinguistic nature.

Thus, scientists do not specifically identify one priority aspect when teaching a foreign language: one should not exclude the other. The priority in this process may be a direction or method, the use of which leads to the improvement of communicative competence.

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